

Adaptation pathways for aquatic plants under climate change: facilitating dispersal and management interventions

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Principal Investigator: Max Finlayson¹

Group Members: Margaret Brock², Cherie Campbell³, Samantha Capon⁴, Michelle Casanova⁵, Adrian Clements², Patrick Driver⁶, Ray Froend⁷, Robert Godfree⁸, Cassandra James⁹, Lindsay Vivian⁸, Jason Nicol¹⁰, Daryl Nielsen³, Jane Roberts¹¹, Arnold Van der Valk¹², Keith Ward¹³

Project Objectives

In a landscape that is predicted to become increasingly managed, wetlands will become either wetter or drier for longer periods and, as a consequence, the ability of biota with limited dispersal mechanisms to re-colonize when favorable conditions occur will be reduced. Recent swings between drought and flood conditions across a large part of Australia have raised questions about how well wetland/riverine plants disperse and re-colonize in the face of changes in water allocations and under climate change.

This ACEAS working group proposed to:

1. **Construct** a listing of wetland and riparian plants from habitats in different parts of Australia
2. **Confirm** and apply the empirical models of life history traits to functional groupings of these species under various water regime scenarios for each region
3. **Develop** response models to projected changes in climate and water regulation.

Methods

A database of wetland plants, including taxonomic detail and fields to describe traits that enable them to survive and disperse was developed. An agreed list of traits was developed and a list of wetland plants compiled from multiple sources, including lists from wetland sites across Australia (Figure 1). The sites provided an indicative although not a representative sample of different wetland environments across Australia (Figures 2-9). The species were allocated to established functional groups based on life history responses to hydrological conditions. The Water Plant Functional Group concept was used to develop other functional groupings based on responses to other climate change parameters, such as elevated temperature or carbon dioxide in the atmosphere.

Information gathered on wetland plant species was also used to analyse the dispersal characteristics of wetland plants, and a model of successional patterns that could develop under a changing climate. A further assessment of the vulnerability of wetland plants to climate change was initiated.

Major Findings

The project has compiled information on aquatic/wetland plant distribution and their life histories from existing datasets and reference materials held across various institutions in both tropical and temperate regions, and from non-tidal wetland ecosystems (e.g. Cowie *et al.* 1986; Rogers and Ralph 2011). This comprises a consolidated dataset of aquatic/wetland plants with specific information on the spatial distribution across geo/climatic regions. The data set can be used as the basis of a national assessment of the conservation status of the species included, and also provide an assessment of the extent and responses of invasive alien species to climate change.

The database contains a listing of all species in hydrological functional groups based on life history traits using established approaches (Brock and Casanova 1997; Brock *et al.* 2003). It has identified a considerable data resource on wetland plants (Cowie *et al.* 1986; Brock *et al.* 2003) and contains sheets:

- **describing sites** (region, name, latitude longitude, height above sea level, Koppen zone, average rainfall, wettest season, annual minimum temperature, annual maximum temperature, source of data, notes)
- **listing species** (subspecies, varieties and forms, with authorities, common names and synonyms according to the Australian Plant Name Index, life-history, whether native or exotic, and references to their ecology)
 - species listed with their **functional group allocation** (WPFPG *sensu* Brock and Casanova 1997, Casanova 2011)
 - species listed with fields for their **salinity response groups**
 - species listed with fields for their **CO₂ response groups**
 - species listed with fields for their **trophic-level response groups**
 - species listed with fields for their **pH response groups**
 - species listed with fields for their **turbidity response groups**
 - species listed with fields for their **grazing response groups**
 - species listed with fields for their **temperature response groups**
- **sites with species presence**

The database is not completely populated, and information is not available for all fields, but the work is on-going. Further effort is required to obtain sufficient information on the ecological responses of aquatic/wetland vegetation to changes in hydrology and climate (Nielsen and Brock 2009; Rogers and Ralph 2011). An empirical model for assessing successional change has been provided and can be used to advise planning for environmental flows, responses to dispersal of aquatic/wetland plants under climate change, or to guide restoration and management of wetlands, including the likely spread of invasive species, whether introduced species, or changes in the distribution of native species. The outcomes can be presented in a conceptual manner to guide decision makers involved in environmental flows, ecological restoration, or determining adaptation opportunities in response to climate change. Researchers can also be encouraged to obtain more specific data to develop quantitative and predictive models for conservation planning.

Key papers or products

- (i) Database on the life history traits of wetland plants and division on a functional grouping and bioregional basis. The database can be kept live and additional data added.
- (ii) Peer reviewed paper on the characterization of life history traits of wetland plants, including alien species, and their geographic distribution and dispersal in relation to climate and landscape features. In prep.
- (iii) Peer reviewed paper on projected dispersal, including seasonal and interannual patterns, of functional groups of wetland plants in response to flow and climate variables. In prep.
- (iv) Peer reviewed paper on successional changes in wetland plants given changes in flows and climate variables, and using examples to illustrate the expected changes. In prep.
- (v) Briefing paper on key knowledge gaps and research priorities for determining the dispersal of wetland plants, including alien species, and for identifying management actions that may be needed to ensure maintenance of specific species or plant types in wetlands. Under consideration.

Figure 1: Approximate locations of wetlands for which species data have been supplied to the database by many researchers around Australia

Figure 2: Young *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* community with understory of grasses and *Pratia concolor* at Moot Yang Gunya Swamp, in the Wimmera region of Victoria. Photo provided by M. Casanova.

Figure 3: Floodplain billabong with *Eucalyptus*, *Eleocharis* and submerged vegetation, near Carnarvon Creek in central Queensland. Photo provided by M. Casanova.

Figure 4: A group of whistling ducks and a spoonbill during the dry, near Fogg Dam, Northern Territory. Photo provided by M. Casanova.

Figure 5: *Ghania filum* community near the Grampians National Park, western Victoria. Photo provided by M. Casanova

Figure 6: Lakeside meadow of herbaceous wetland plants (*Myriophyllum*, *Eleocharis*, *Rumex*, *Crassula*, *Lythrum*) at the recently restored Lake Condah Indigenous Protected Area, western Victoria. Photo provided by M. Casanova.

Figure 7: Moments before a filling event in a *Melaleuca* swamp in the south west of Western Australia. Photo provided by M. Casanova.

Figure 8: Streamers of *Triglochin* in Rocky River, a pristine water way, on Kangaroo Island, South Australia. Photo provided by M. Casanova.

Figure 8: *Melaleuca quinquenervia* open forest with *Blechnum procerum*, *Baumea rubiginosa* and *Gahnia sieberana* understory at Eighteen Mile Swamp, North Stradbroke Island, Queensland. Photo by A. Specht.

How will this affect Australian ecosystem science & management?

The project has provided synthesized information that will enable water and wetland managers determine, at a functional group level, the ability of wetland plants to disperse given fragmentation of floodplain wetland systems, and disruptions or reductions in flows. Undertaking such determinations at a functional group level should reduce the complexity of dealing with multiple species, often with limited knowledge about their biology, geographic distribution and responses to flow and climate scenario. This can be done using a successional model based on life history traits to understand where plant succession, as well as dispersal features contribute to the ability of such plants to move and re/establish in specific wetlands. The site-based component of the database can be used to investigate regional level responses.

Further analysis is required to develop further functional groups and how these respond to other climate drivers, such as increased temperatures or atmospheric carbon dioxide. It is anticipated that these models will be able to provide diagrammatic representation of responses. Further assessment of the vulnerability of functional groups to climate change is needed, in particular to find ways to represent their sensitivity and resilience.

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